

Origins of the Rohingya Crisis in Bangladesh: A Contextual and Legal Review

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Abstract:

[The 1982 Burmese Citizenship Act fails to acknowledge Rohingyas as citizens of Myanmar, leaving them without a state. Consequently, many have sought refuge in Bangladesh, with over 10,000 settling in temporary camps across Cox's Bazar, Teknaf, and Ukha. These displaced Rohingyas rely entirely on aid from the Bangladeshi government, the United Nations, and various international non-governmental organizations for their survival. The Rohingya crisis has evolved into a significant burden for Bangladesh and poses a threat to the security of other nations in South and Southeast Asia. While resolving this crisis is crucial, a swift solution seems improbable. Myanmar asserts that the Rohingyas are undocumented immigrants from Bangladesh and, along with the country's Buddhist majority, rejects them as part of their nation. This stance sparks complex debates surrounding history, identity, and religion. Comprehending this crisis requires delving into the history of the Rohingyas in Arakan, now known as Rakhine State. To find a solution that really lasts, we need to look back at the history and social and political changes of the Rohingya people in the Arakan region. This research wants to help the conversation about this topic by exploring the Rohingya's history and how it connects to the problems they face now. The study uses both primary and secondary sources. We did field surveys close to Rohingya camps and talked to local people, government and non-government organization workers, diplomats, experts and border security people from both Bangladesh and Myanmar. We used descriptive and analytical methods to understand the data better, aiming to create a more well-informed and lasting solution to this humanitarian crisis.]

Keywords: Arakan, Bangladesh, Identity Crisis, Myanmar, Persecution, Refugee, Rohingya,

Introduction

The Rohingyas are the Muslim population of Arakan. Now it is a part of Myanmar. Who are the Rohingyas and why is this crisis? This is a vital question to the intellectuals of the modern times. Why does this question arise again and again among the scholars or the intellectuals? Clearly, there are some historical as well as geo-political causes behind the question. As a result, to discuss the origin of the Rohingya crisis it is better for us that we gradually analyse the origin of the words Arakan, and Rohingya as well as the Muslim settlement in Arakan with their early history and finally why is this crisis?

After being officially excluded from the country in 1982 by the Burmese citizenship law, the Rohingyas are primarily a racial, linguistic, and Muslim minority group that is not a citizen. The Rohingyas are widely acknowledged as one of the most persecuted ethnic groups in the world, according to the United Nations (UN). They have lived in Myanmar for generations, but they are routinely refused citizenship and face a number of harsh limitations. These include requiring official approval to marry or have more than two children, as well as the obligation to notify authorities if they wish to leave their villages. This discrimination has contributed to the community's enduring marginalization and statelessness" (Border, 2012). Since 1978, they are being persecuted by the Burmese government. Currently, more than one million Rohingyas have fled and took sheltered in the camps of Ukhia, Cox's Bazar, a district of Bangladesh. This study adopts a historical methodology and relies primarily on secondary sources, including books, journal articles, newspaper articles, and online resources.

Objectives

The objectives of this research are:

1. To examine the historical origins and emergence of the Rohingya crisis in Myanmar.
2. To identify the root causes of ethno-religious conflict.

To identify and analyze the instances of genocide perpetrated against the Rohingya population in Myanmar.

Literature Review

Rai and Sharma reviewed existing research on the Rohingya refugee crisis. They explained the issue using theories of securitization, structural violence, and ethnic identity (Sharma, 2020). The Rohingyas are a Muslim minority group in Myanmar who has faced discrimination and violence for many years. Many have fled to countries like Bangladesh, Malaysia, and Thailand. Violence against the Rohingyas is not always physical. It also happens through laws and policies that limit their rights. They are denied citizenship, freedom of movement, and access to basic services (Cheeseman, 2017). The Rohingyas are treated as outsiders in Myanmar and are not recognized as part of the nation (Chan, 2005). The 1982 Citizenship Law made them stateless, increasing their struggles (Cowley, 2014).

Their situation has worsened due to right-wing Buddhist nationalism and military rule. These forces have further oppressed the Rohingyas and taken away their political rights.

Ullah and Chatteraj discuss the history of Rohingya persecution in Myanmar. They explain different ways the Rohingyas have suffered under government policies and social discrimination (Ullah A.K.M, 2018). Md. Shayed Hossain also examines the root causes of the Rohingya crisis, explaining how the Myanmar government has contributed to their suffering (Hossain M. S., Bangladesh-Myanmar Relations; 1972-2010, 2014) (Hossain M. S., 5 Decades of Rohingya refugees' crisis: A security quandary for Bangladesh, 2025).

Maximum researcher has written the way of persecution, how the Rohingyas suffered by the Myanmar government and their policies. However, the actual causes behind the Rohingyas crisis were discussed in a scattered manner, it did not comprehensively explore and analyse. Here, this is a large gap in regarding the origin of the Rohingya crisis. In this research, researchers try to fill the existing research gap.

Materials and Method

This study uses a historical, descriptive, and qualitative approach. It collects and analyzes information from different sources, including both primary and secondary data.

Primary Data Sources

The study conducts semi-structured interviews with Rohingya refugees, Bangladeshi government officials, NGO representatives, historians, and experts on Rohingya refugees from both Bangladesh and Myanmar sides, Border Guard Police (BGP), Border Guard Bangladesh (BGB), and diplomats from various countries.

Field Observations

Visits to refugee camps and border areas help document real causes of the crisis.

Secondary Data Sources

Secondary information is colonial records and Myanmar's 1982 Citizenship Law, Historical migration patterns, Reports from the Bangladesh government, UNHCR, and IOM, Books and journal articles on ethnic conflicts, statelessness, and forced migration, Media reports from Bangladesh, Myanmar, and international sources.

This study follows a fully qualitative method. Primary data comes from open-ended interviews with refugees, experts, and INGO workers. Secondary data helps analyze existing research. The study applies the open coding approach of grounded theory to find important themes in the collected data.

Novelty of Research

This study deeply explores the history of the Rohingya crisis. It traces their origins to early Muslim settlements in Arakan, including Arab traders and Mughal influences. Unlike many studies that rely only on books and reports, this research uses direct interviews, group discussions, and field visits to gather real-life information. It makes a unique connection between the Rohingyas' history and their current statelessness under Myanmar's 1982 Citizenship Law. This study also looks at the crisis as more than just a human rights issue. It shows how the situation affects the security of Bangladesh and the entire South Asian region.

Contribution to Knowledge

The study helps answer a key question: Are the Rohingyas native to Myanmar or migrants from Bengal? By using historical records and colonial documents, it supports the idea that the Rohingyas have lived in Myanmar for centuries. It also highlights how the Rohingyas face structural violence. This includes restrictions on movement, marriage, land ownership, and education. The study provides a clear picture of state-led discrimination against them. This research goes beyond Myanmar and Bangladesh. Unlike other studies that only focus on political oppression, this research also explores how Buddhist nationalism, particularly the 969 Movement, has increased hatred against the Rohingyas. Finally, this study successfully exposed the factual causes of the Rohingya crisis.

Fulfillment of Research Gap

This study adds historical depth, firsthand evidence, and a security viewpoint to the Rohingya crisis. It provides important new knowledge to existing research. Most studies focus only on recent refugee crises, such as those in 2012 and 2017. This research fills the gap by giving a full historical timeline from the 8th century to today. It explains how the crisis developed over a long period. While many studies rely only on UN reports and media

articles, this study uses real interviews with Rohingya refugees, Bangladeshi officials, and NGOs. Most research focuses only on the humanitarian side of the crisis. By carefully analyzing Myanmar's 1982 Citizenship Law, this study explains how it has caused long-term statelessness for the Rohingyas. It adds new discussions on legal aspects of Rohingya rights.

Results and Discussion

The Rohingya Muslims are the people of Arakan. To understand who they are, we need to know about the history of Muslim settlement in Arakan. Arab Muslim traders had strong connections with Arakan and the coastal areas of the Bay of Bengal. They played a key role in both trade and spreading Islam in these regions. In the 8th century, Arab Muslims came to Arakan for business. They followed the trading traditions of their ancestors. At that time, Arab traders were very active in sea trade and controlled much of the business in the East. The Rohingya Muslims in Arakan are settled in some phases. Important phases are as following;

First Phase

“In the 8th and 9th centuries, the Arabs were foremost sea-faring and maritime people of the world and the Arab merchants sailed across all waters too far off countries of the East and the West..... The eastern trade of the Arab merchants flourished so much so that the Indian Ocean and Bay of Bengal turned into Arab lakes” (Rahim, 1963). In this connection, we have an interesting myth or spiritual story about the first coming of the Muslims in these regions although, we don't have any exact evident like date and year behind it. “It was not but the most interesting legend in the society of Arakan regarding the coming of Muhammad bin Hanifa, son of Hazrat Ali (R.), the 4th Caliph of Islam to Arakan. On the basis of this legend Shah Barid khan wrote a book (*Puthi*) in 16th century named *Hanifa-o-Kaiyapari*” (Uddin, 2012). This event has narrated by some writers that “In 680 A.D. after the tragedy war of '*Karbala*' Muhammad Hanifiya with his army

arrived Arab Shah Para near Maungdaw in the North Arakan, while Kaiyapari, the queen of the cannibals ruled this hilly deep forest attacking and looting the people of Arakan” (Siddiquee, Who are the Rohingya and How? Origin and Development of the Rohingyas in Arakan, 2012). Muhammad Hanifiya led an assault against the cannibalistic tribes and successfully captured their queen. Over time, the queen embraced Islam and entered into marriage with Hanifiya. This conversion led to the wider acceptance of Islam among her followers. The couple then settled in the Mayu Range, where they resided in the region's peaks, which came to be known as Hanifa Tonki and Kaiyapari Tonki in recognition of their presence. Under Hanifiya's leadership, the previously savage cannibalistic tribes were subdued and underwent a process of civilization. “The followers of Muhammad Hanif and Kaiyapari were mixed and live peacefully” (Habibullah, 1995). The historical accuracy of the legend surrounding Hazrat Ali (R.)'s marriage to a woman from the Hanafia tribe and the subsequent birth of her son, Muhammad ibn Hanafia, remains a subject of scholarly debate. After the death of Hazrat Fatima (R.), it is reported that Hazrat Ali (R.) married a woman from the Hanafia tribe, and their son was named Muhammad ibn Hanafia, rather than Muhammad ibn Ali (R.). However, the historical veracity of later events related to Muhammad ibn Hanafia, as well as the accounts surrounding the figures of Hanifa Tonki and Kaiyapari Tonki, are difficult to confirm and remain shrouded in mystery. If this legend were to be substantiated, one might speculate that the descendants of these mixed lineages could have played a significant role in the formation of the early Muslim community in Arakan. However, due to the lack of concrete evidence, these connections remain speculative and require further historical examination.

Second Phase

The second time Muslims came to Arakan is an important event in history. This story is

narrated in the traditional history of Arakan. It was stated in all the local history of Arakan. In the legendary history of the Kings of Ra-Dz-Wang, it has been reported that many Kula or Arab ships wrecked on the Ramree Islands, during the rule of the Arakanese King, Mahataing Tsandaya (788-810 A.D.). Surprisingly, all the Muslims sailors were rescued by the help of the local people. The people took them to the local administration as well as the king (Karim, 2000). The King noted all the Muslim mariner's skill and cultural attitudes and life. Later, the king granted to them some of the land and allowed them to live there, too. This strongly supports the idea that Arab traders were in contact with Arakan, which is very close to Bengal, as early as the 8th century. R.B. Smart mentions this in the British Burma Gazetteer as follows.

“Local historical accounts indicate that during the ninth century, several ships were wrecked off the Coast of Ramree Island, with the Muslim crews subsequently taken to Arakan and settled in various villages. These Muslim settlers closely resembled the local Arakanese population in many aspects, differing primarily in their religion and the social customs dictated by their faith. While they adopted Burmese script for written communication, they continued to speak their ancestral language in everyday conversation.” (Smart, 1917).

In this regard, Abdul Karim, a prominent historian, discusses, analyzes and reflects that: “This is a very important piece of evidence regarding the origin of the Rohingyas. These shipwrecked Arab Muslims became the nucleus of the Muslim population of Arakan; later other Muslims from Arabia, Persia and other countries entered into Arakan. The important point to be noticed about these shipwrecked Muslims is that they have stuck to their religion, i. e. Islam and Islamic social customs. Though they used Burmese language and also adopted other local customs, they have retained the language of their

ancestors (probably with mixture of local words) in dealing among themselves. Another point to be noted is that the Arab shipwrecked Muslims have retained their religion, language and their social customs for more than thousand years. Later on, of course other Arabs also come in the trading and other pursuits and some of them have stayed on in Arkan and in this way people of Arab blood increased as time passed by. So the Rohingyas have been staying in Arakan for more than a thousand years” (Karim, 2000).

“It may at best say that the Arabs made the port of Chittagong either a halting place or a commercial station, convenient to the purpose of trade in the neighbouring areas and it is obvious that if the traders had trade contact with Chittagong, then of course, the Arakanese coast was not excluded” (Chowdhury M. A., *The Advent of Islam in Arakan and the Rohingyas*, 2006). Over time, the Muslim population in Arakan grew. These Muslims built strong and friendly relationships with the local people. Many of them married local women and became part of the community. It was a common tradition in Arakan for foreign visitors, traders, or shipwrecked sailors to marry local women and settle there.

According to Mohammad Ali Chowdhury “hundreds of saints and their followers came, in different times, to Bengal and the Arakan region, from Persia and other Muslim lands along the old established sea-route and spread themselves in towns and remote villages” (Chowdhury M. A., *The Advent of Islam in Arakan and the Rohingyas*, 2006). These Sufi-saints had tried to call the masses of Islam among the people and they had a great influence in this region. According to the Arakanese traditional history, during the king Anawarhta (1044-1077) many Sufis came to Arakan for travelling. Many pieces of evidence show that Muslim saints came to Arakan a long time ago. They played an important role in spreading Islam and helping the Muslim community grow and develop.

Third Phase

During the third phase, a ruler named Naramekhla, also known as Min Sowa Mun (1404-1434), played a key role in connecting Muslims with Arakan both strategically and culturally. He was the grandson of Minthi, a former king of Arakan. According to Arakanese history, Min Sowa Mun took Saw Pu Nyo, the sister of his minister Aananda Them, by force. This angered the minister, who then sought help from the Ava King, Min Swe Min Khaung, to attack Min Sowa Mun known as Naramekhla. The Ava king sent his son, Min Ye Kyaw Swa, to lead the attack. Min Ye Kyaw Swa defeated Min Sowa Mun and removed him from power.

In 1406, the Burmese king invaded Arakan, forcing Naramekhla to flee. He sought refuge in Gaur, the capital of the Bengal Sultanate. At that time, Giasuddin Azam Shah (1390-1411), son of Sultan Sikandar Shah (1358-1390), was the ruler of Bengal. However, he was unable to assist Naramekhla immediately, as he was occupied with other important political and administrative matters (Siddiquee, 2014). The defeated king, Naramekhla, was treated with great respect and allowed to stay in Bengal. As a result, he spent a large part of his life there. In 1430, with the help of Sultan Jalaluddin Mohammed Shah of Bengal (who ruled from 1415 to 1432), Naramekhla was able to return to his throne in Arakan. However, the process of his restoration was fraught with difficulty. Initially, the Sultan of Bengal dispatched an army of 20,000 soldiers, commanded by General Wali Khan, to assist in the king's reinstatement. Upon reaching Arakan, Wali Khan, seeing an opportunity to assert his own authority, betrayed the king and imprisoned Min Sowa Mun, the Arakanese ruler. The king, however, managed to escape and sought refuge once again with his patron, Sultan Jalaluddin. In response to this betrayal, Sultan Jalaluddin Mohammed Shah sent a second, larger expedition in 1430, consisting of 30,000 troops led by General Sandi Khan. The mission had two

objectives: to restore Min Sowa Mun to his throne and to punish Wali Khan for his treachery. Sandi Khan, a skilled and capable military leader, succeeded in both tasks. He reinstated Min Sowa Mun as king of Arakan and ensured the execution of Wali Khan, thus reasserting Bengali influence in the region. (Chowdhury M. A., *Bengal - Arakan Relations*, 2004). The interesting matter is that after the king's restoration, the army from Bengal did not come back from Arakan, but they had to stay for the help of the restored King in Arakan.

King Naramekhla was given the title Solaiman Shah and started a new ruling family called the Maruk-U dynasty. The capital of this dynasty was Mrohaung. From the beginning, the Arakan kingdom had to pay tribute to Bengal. The kings of Arakan used Muslim names and introduced coins with the *Kalima*. This tradition continued until the first half of the 17th century. "From this time onwards the relation of Muslims with the Arakanese became more intimate and for about two centuries Arakan was united in a bond of friendship with Islamic lands" (Chowdhury M. A., 2006). "As a result of the impact of the civilization of the Muslims, Arakanese culture also progressed and thus began the 'Golden Age' in the history of Arakan" (Chowdhury M. A., *The Advent of Islam in Arakan and the Rohingyas*, 2006).

It is very well known that Chittagong has been under almost unabated Arakan rule for nearly a century, from 1580 to 1666, but although the Arakanese retained these possessions in Bengal, it appears as an agricultural work that numbers of the population were sent into Arakan. In addition, in the 16th and 17th centuries the Arakanese (known as Maghs in Bengal) organized a plundering group in connection with the Portuguese adventures. They ravaged and destroyed large parts of Southern and Eastern Bengal. Many men, women and children were taken away as prisoners from Bengal's coastal districts. And the Maghs used them for

agricultural work. We are well aware that the kingdom of Arakan was a barely settled region, needing too much human labor for cultivation. In that respect, in the village of land at the banks of the Kaladan river, Arakanese hired a significant number of prisoners to the Naaf river.

The fourth and the last major wave of Muslim migration from Bengal to Arakan took place during the rule of Mughal Emperor Shah Jahan, who reigned from 1627 to 1658. Shah Jahan had four sons: Dara Shikoh, Shah Shuja, Aurangzeb, and Murad. These princes were skilled in warfare, governance, and administration. However, Shah Jahan foresaw that, upon his death, his sons would inevitably contest each other for the throne of Delhi. However, in 1660 the Mughal Prince Shah Shuja fled from Delhi and took sheltered in Arakan. This event carried out a new chapter of Muslim migrations to the territory of Arakan and also caused political changed. The Mughal prince did not go alone to Arakan rather he was accompanied by his entire family as well as his faithful soldiers.

Very cordially, the Prince was welcomed as well as received at Arakan by the Arakanise king, Sonda Thudamma. “The prince was also allowed to settle there under the royal protection. But as days rolled on it seemed that the attitude of the Raja Sonda Thudamma was becoming colder and ultimately became hostile to the refugee Prince” (Chowdhury M. , 1996). “Whatever might be the reason, Prince Shah Shuja, his wife, sons, daughters and other family members were also ignominiously murdered at Mrohaung (Mrauk-U), the capital of Arakan, in 1661” (Chowdhury M. A., Bengal - Arakan Relations, 2004, p. 134). “But those escaped the massacre were later admitted into the king’s bodyguard as a special archers unit called *Kamans or Kamanci*” (Chowdhury M. A., The Advent of Islam in Arakan and the Rohingyas, 2006). Between 1666 and 1710 Arakan's political control was fully in their possession during which king makers and

breakers were given a vital function to Muslim Kaman units. Over time, more Muslims arrived from Upper India. Their descendants still live on the island of Ramree and in some villages near Akyab. They speak Arakanese and follow similar customs and manners as the Arakanese people, except for practicing Islam.

The identity of the Rohingya Muslims

“The Muslims of Arakan are the clear descendants of a race of early Muslims. They are the descendants of the Muslim Arabs, Moors, Persians, Turks, Mughals and Bengalis who came mostly as traders, warriors and saints through overland and sea-route” (Chowdhury M. A., 2006). Many settled down in Arakan and the present production of the "Rohingyas" became mixed up with the local population. Some claim the phrase 'Rohingya' derives from the word 'Raham' in Arabic, which means solidarity. According to the Mohammad Ali Chowdhury “it was during the reign of king Mahayn-at-chandra some Arab ships were wrecked along the shores of Arakan and the ill-fated people who boarded on them, begged for help by uttering Raham, Raham, Raham. Gradually it changed from Raham to Rohang and finally they were named Rohingyas” (Chowdhury M. A., 2006). “Hence the Muslim populations around Mrohaung, the capital of Arakan, are known to be Rohingyas” (Chowdhury M. , 1996). “There is an alternative concept that the term “Rohingya” is actually used to describe the Ruha people who migrated from Afghanistan” (Mohajan H. K., 2018).

The Roang / Rohang / Roshang word is, of course, the false shape of the old title of Mrohaung, the Arakan capital. The people staying in Rohang or Roshang are ultimately regarded as Roshangee or Rohingya. Two separate groups are present in the Muslim community of Chittagong; one is called 'Chatganiya,' and the rest is called 'Rohai. “Even the concluding forms half the total population of Chittagong, who trace their origin to Arakan or Mrohaung. Since Chittagong was an integral part of the Arakanese kingdom till the first half of the

seventeenth century (Chowdhury M. A., Bengal - Arakan Relations, 2004). “The people of Chittagong were expected to work in the capital of Arakan to represent the kings in different roles: nobles, traders and staff etc. As the South Chittagong is close to Arakan, the inhabitants of this area are called Rosangi or Ruhaingya by the people of North Chittagong” (Chowdhury M. , 1996). Siddiquee noted that “In course of time these Rosang (Rohang) and Rosangi (Rohingya) are treated for Arakan and people of Arakan respectively. So, it is clear that Rosanga is infact, a corruption form of Mrohang> Rohang> Rosang or Rosanga” (Siddiquee, 2014, p. 30).

Rohingyas' history shows that they have arisen from numerous stocks of people clustered in a specific geographical area. They have an ancient history, spiritual, historic and civilizational heritage, which is more than 1,200 years old and is reflected in the shrines, cemeteries, sanctuaries, religious and educational structures that are spread all over the country today. Moshe Yegar notes that “the Rohingyas preserved their own heritage from the impact of the Buddhist environment, not only as far as their religion is concerned, but also in their culture” (Yegar, 1972). “Language is the main foundation of culture and the Rohingyas have developed a language of their own from Arabic, Sanskrit, Bengali and Urdu which serves as common source of contact with in the Rohingya community. They have also songs and music of their own.” (Bahar, 2010).

According to the census in 1911, “the Rohingyas were included with the Indian population as an ethnic group Indian origin. The reason given was that they looked more like Indians than like Burmese. On the other, the census of 1921 mentions the Rohingyas as really Arakanese but so close to Indians that the phenomenon is as much an annexation of India” (Grantham, 1923). “However, this census anomaly of counting the Rohingyas as Indians no doubt contributed to the present controversy over

the Rohingyas origin in Burma. But the Rohingyas claim that in terms of their culture they are neither Indian nor Burmese” (Mohajan H. , 2018). A British military officer who worked mostly on Arakan front during the World War II commented on Arakan Muslims' racial existence as follows:

“To look at, they are quite unlike any other product of India and Burma that I have seen. They resemble the Arab in name, in dress and in habit. The women and the young girls have a distinctive Arab touch about them” (Irwin, 1945).

So, Rohingya's ethnic origin was traced back to the latter part of the 7th century, when Arakan was established to the first Muslim inhabitant. Rohingya Muslims have also been identified by numerous sources; as the Rohingyas, who live predominantly in the state of Arakan, in Burma, are a Muslim minority community, while about 800,000 Rohingya live in Burma and their descendants have reportedly been in the country for hundreds of years. The Government of Burma does not accept the people of Rohingya as residents; as a result, citizens without a state are being brutally abused in Burma and in the Bangladesh, neighboring refugee camps.

According to the UNHCR “Rohingyas are virtually friendless among Myanmar’s other ethnic and religious communities. Anti-Rohingya as well as anti-Muslim attitude has long tainted the Myanmar’s political and societal spheres.” The Burmese army has been regularly abusing the human rights of the Rohingyas since 1962, including murder, kidnapping, torture, etc. The Rohingya and other Muslims are further caused by such a horrific human rights and humanitarian crisis like ‘statelessness’. Despite the protection of the right to nationality under the Universal Declaration of Human Rights preventing their unconstitutional deprivation, the Burmese Citizenship Act, passed in 1982, codified Rohingya's constitutional absence and restricted similar citizen status. This rejection of Burma's citizenship has definitely contributed to other

gaps and disadvantages, including the lack of access by the community to identification papers, education and occupations. It has also left members of the party vulnerable to illegal imprisonment, slave labor and discrimination against taxes. The government of Burma has further limited its marriage, possessing property and freedom of travel rights granted by international law and non-citizens. Even worse, Burma president Thein Sein remains uncompromisingly opposed to abolishing or amending the 1982 Citizenship Act and before the oppressive clauses of the legislation are repealed, the status of Rohingya Muslims will not change.

What is the Rohingya Issue?

The Rohingya issue is a long-standing and complex conflict rooted in historical, ethnic, and political factors. The Rohingyas are a Muslim ethnic group primarily residing in the cities of Buthidaung and Maungdaw in Rakhine State, Myanmar, near the Naaf River, which forms the border with Bangladesh. They coexist with the Buddhist Arakanese and Burmese people, but their exact population remains unknown due to the absence of a formal census (Maizland, 2020). The term 'Rohingya' has historical roots, with one of its earliest recorded uses appearing in an official address presented to Burmese Prime Minister U Nu on March 10, 1950 (Nemoto, 2014).

Historical Background

The Rohingyas trace their history back to the Mrauk-U dynasty (1430–1785) in the Arakan Kingdom. However, significant demographic changes occurred during British colonial rule after the First Anglo-Burmese War (1824–1826) (Cleaver, 2024). The British encouraged migration from India, including from Chittagong (now in Bangladesh), which fueled tensions between the Muslim and Buddhist communities. During the Japanese invasion of Burma (1942–1945), this divide deepened as the Japanese armed the Buddhist Arakanese while the British

supported Muslim forces against the Japanese. These hostilities resulted in severe casualties and long-term animosities between the two groups (Martin, 2010).

Post-Independence Developments

Following Burma's independence in 1948, efforts to foster peaceful coexistence between Muslims and Buddhists in Arakan largely failed, particularly after General Ne Win seized power in 1962. The military regime excluded the Rohingyas from the list of 135 officially recognized ethnic groups in 1989, reinforcing the narrative that they were illegal immigrants from Bangladesh (Maizland, 2020). This stance originated under Ne Win's government (1962–1988), despite previous recognition of the Rohingyas as an ethnic group under the U Nu administration (1948-1958 and 1960-1962).

The 1974 Emergency Immigration Act and the 1982 Burmese Citizenship Law further marginalized the Rohingyas, as they were denied citizenship and issued Foreign Registration Certificates (FRC) instead of National Registration Certificates (NRC) (Rohingya: Issues relating to Statelessness, 2021), (Council, 2023). Some Rohingyas sought NRCs by identifying as members of recognized Muslim groups, such as the Kamans.

Mass Displacements and Refugee Crisis

The Rohingya crisis escalated with the first major exodus in 1978, following the Burmese government's "Operation Dragon King," which aimed to register and classify all residents to determine their citizenship status (Yegar M., Between integration and secession: the Muslim communities of the southern Philippines, Southern Thailand, and western Burma/Myanmar, 2002). This operation led to the expulsion of 200,000 to 250,000 Rohingyas, who fled to Bangladesh. In response, Bangladesh's President Ziaur Rahman condemned Myanmar's actions, but the Burmese government insisted that those

expelled were illegal immigrants. Under international pressure from the United Nations (UN), UNHCR, Saudi Arabia, India, and the World Muslim League, Myanmar agreed to repatriate 200,000 Rohingya refugees in 1979.

However, the Rohingyas' return did not improve their situation. The lack of citizenship, land confiscation, and forced labor exacerbated their plight. Another mass exodus occurred between April 1991 and May 1992, when over 250,000 Rohingyas fled due to military persecution (Mallick, 2020). Bangladesh sought international assistance, leading to UNHCR's involvement in providing aid and negotiating repatriation agreements between Myanmar and Bangladesh in 1992 and 1993. These agreements, however, failed to ensure long-term security for the Rohingyas.

The 2012 Ethnic Violence and Renewed Crisis

Ethnic tensions reignited in 2012, following the rape and murder of a Rakhine woman, allegedly by three Rohingya men. The violence resulted in at least 50 deaths and the displacement of 30,000 people. The Myanmar government largely ignored the crisis, prompting another wave of Rohingya refugees crossing into Bangladesh in June 2012. Bangladesh provided initial assistance but refused long-term settlement, citing socio-economic concerns and security risks, including the potential presence of militants among the refugees.

Current Situation and Humanitarian Concerns

The Myanmar government continues to deny the Rohingyas citizenship and restricts their movement. They are not issued NRCs and are confined to specific areas such as Maungdaw and Buthidaung unless they pay high fees. Simultaneously, the government has been resettling Buddhist Arakanese in Rohingya-dominated regions, intensifying communal tensions. Reports of illegal human trafficking and security challenges related to Rohingya

movements persist, complicating regional stability.

Oppression on the Rohingya

“The United Nations described Rohingya as one of the biggest groups and one of the most oppressed minorities in the world” (Kiragu, 2011). The Rohingya Muslims' discrimination and injustice in Arakan stems from the disrespect of Myanmar's government. The efforts to suppress the Rohingya are as follows;

“Arakan Muslims are excluded from their employment and replaced by Buddhists, all sorts of Islamic institutions, organisations and schools are closed down, and all Rohingya land has been seized and transferred to Buddhists. Finally, the Government of Burma has indeed sought to demonstrate that Muslims are terrorists”.

“Muslim persecution in Burma started during the reign of the King Bodawpayar (1782–1819)” (Siddiquee, 2014). “The first suffering of the Muslims of Rohingya in Myanmar began in 1784 due to the fear of the spread of Islam in the region” (Bahar, 2010). The Rohingyas were subjected to unceasing persecution under the military rule of General Ne Win between 1966 and 1988. In 1978 a large-scale census operation called Dragon King (Nagamin) was reported to get the Rohingyas as illegal immigrants expelled. This aggressive strategy executed by the Government of Myanmar (GoM) has demolished mosques and several Islamic historic buildings and a lot of historical schools. “The Rohingya are destructive in these respects, such as: violence, rape, poverty, torture and 50 Rohingya's murder, which forced to migrate from Northern Arakan to Bangladesh was forced to take place of over 200,000 Rohingya” (Grundy-Warr, 1997). Since the 1970s, many violent attacks on the Rohingya have driven and more than ten lakh Rohingya have migrated to neighbouring countries like Bangladesh. “The Rohingya suffered not only from discrimination under the 1982 Citizenship Act, but also from social injustice, such as the denial of their basic human rights” (Azad, 2013).

“In the 1983 nationwide census, Rohingya were completely excluded” (Matthieson, 1955). “From 1991-1992, more than 250,000 Rohingya refugees fled from Myanmar and arrived in Bangladesh, living in temporary camps” (Grundy-Warr, 1997). Hostility against the Rohingyas emerged from strongly ingrained Buddhist nationalism and intensified anti-Rohingya emotions, such as disbelief, intense displeasure, and perceived Rohingya terror in a Buddhist culture. In the Rakhine Province, serious violence between the Buddhists and the Rohingyas erupted between June and November 2012. “At least 200,000 Rohingyas in the Rakhine State have fled their homes since June 2012” (Holmes, 2015). “The UN Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs reports that more than 143,500 remain internally displaced in Rakhine as of August 2015” (UNOCHA, 2015). From 2012 to 2016 the violence in Rakhine State has taken at least 1,000 lives and has internally displaced over 140,000. “In May 2015, about 139 graves suspected to be Rohingya from Myanmar were discovered on the Thai Malaysian border” (Pitman, 2015). “The Nay-Sat Kut-kwey ye (NaSaKa), a security force consisting of police, military, intelligence, customs officers, and riot police, operated in Rakhine State until 2013 under the control of the Ministry for Border Affairs” (Selth, 2012). The Myanmar Army and NaSaKa compelled the Rohingya to participate in forced labor. “They destroyed unauthorized mosques and about 5,000 homes of the Rohingya and closed mosques and Islamic schools, and used them as government administrative offices” (Mohajan H. , 2018). “The GoM enforces strict restrictions on the freedom of movement of the Rohingya” (HRW, 2012).

“Rohingya women and girls of Rohingyas have been raped and sexually assaulted by the Army of Myanmar, NaSaKa as well as Myanmar Police. Some women have died as a result of gang rapes” (UNHCR, Text of the 1961 Convention on the Reduction of Statelessness. Geneva, Switzerland., 2016). In the 1990s, Myanmar

enacted a law which required authorization for all people in the State of Rakhin before they were given marriage permits. The GoM reported that Rohingya reproduces more rapidly than international norms. In order for marriage licenses to be issued, men must remove their beards and women must not wear a hair or hair head as well as face covering for their authorization pictures. “The Rohingya women must also take pregnancy tests before they request wedding permissions” (Lindblom, 2015). In summary, the Rohingyas have faced many serious abuses. They also suffer from unfair rules like the two-child policy, political arrests, and long detentions. Many have been forced to leave their homes, move to other places, or had their land and belongings taken away. Their houses and businesses have been burned down, and they are often forced to work without pay, including children. Some have been victims of human trafficking or locked inside fenced areas. Mosques have been destroyed, and their basic freedoms such as moving freely, gathering in groups, expressing opinions, and practicing religion have been severely restricted. (Commission, 2005).

There is a movement that is considered as the influence of recent conflict between the Burmese and the Rohingya as follows:

The 969 Movement

The extremist movement of Buddhist monks in Myanmar is known as 969. Virathu is the one who started the movement from the grassroots. He is also known as "Burmese bin Laden". Virathu has boycotted Muslim businesses in Myanmar. He also declared it forbidden to associate with the Muslim community. He identified mosques as enemy bases. Virathu's name has been repeatedly mentioned in various incidents of violence against Muslims in Myanmar. According to a report in the Wall Street Journal, the number 969 represents three Buddhist ideologies. The first 9 signifies the nine special powers of the Buddha, the 6 refers to the six teachings of the Buddha, and the last 9 refers

to the nine special symbols of the Sangha or Buddhist doctrine. The movement's leader says their goal is to maintain Buddhist dominance in Myanmar. They think that Muslims are destroying the dominance of Buddhists by surviving like parasites. After independence from Britain in 1947, Muslims held senior government positions in Myanmar. This situation changed in 1982. At this time, the army seized power in Myanmar. The military has instilled in the people of that country an attitude that Muslims are controlling Myanmar's business. Muslims have been accused of building mosques for profit. He is marrying Buddhists. In this way Islamic rule is being established. The question is, why do Buddhists have such an attitude towards Muslims? Muslims do not go to Buddhist restaurants because of religious customs. For this reason, the restaurant business is dominated by Muslims. Muslim-owned companies make business trips to Myanmar. Such as, Nying Group, Motherland, Fatherland. As a result, as Muslims became more successful in business, the negative attitude of Buddhists towards them increased in Myanmar. This movement has a strong influence in Myanmar and beyond, although the movement was harshly criticized in the international media. Asin Weirathu blames movement leader for recent anti-Muslim violence, (Reports Straits Times). Various media outlets have branded the movement anti-Muslim and "Islam phobic (GALACHE). However, Buddhist supporters in Myanmar deny calling the movement Islamophobic. The leader of the movement, Weirathu, called the movement "a movement to protect the Rakhine (Buddhists) from Bengali terrorists." Another source claimed that the number 969 was introduced as the opposite of the three numbers 786 that are well-known among Muslims across South Asia (The Atlantic: 2013). Moreover, 969 supporters interpret it as confirmation of a Muslim invasion of Burma in the 21st century on the grounds that 7 plus 8 plus 6 is equivalent to 21 (The Atlantic: 2013).

The Campaign 969 is a cultural movement in several Buddhist countries to uphold the cultural tradition and spiritual values of Buddhism. This movement was made up of by the prominent Buddhist monk Ashin wirathu, also known as the "Burmese Bin Laden," (Mohajan H. , 2018). In other countries including Thailand and Sri Lanka the Movement is rising rapidly (Walton, 2013). Ashin Wirathu was arrested in 2003 for 25 years for creating religious conflict. However, he was released in January 2012 as part of a general pardon. The term 969 has a special meaning in Buddhism. The first 9 represents Buddha's divine qualities. The number 6 in the middle stands for His six enlightenments. The last 9 represents the good qualities of Buddhist monks (Sangha).

The 969 movement was first introduced in a study by U Kyaw Lwin, a government worker in the Ministry of Religious Affairs during the 1990s. He passed away in 2001. This movement is linked to the Three Jewels (Tiratana) of Buddhism. Some extremist Buddhists claim that the movement does not support illegal activities, sinful acts, sexual abuse, or the exploitation of women. The 969-campaign started in Myanmar as part of a national movement.

"Stickers printed with the 969 logos were distributed for free to be attached at various spots, such as shops, vehicles, bus stops, and homes" (Hayward, 2014). Former President Thein Sein's office has painted the 969 logos as an indication of the peace symbol, and the President called it a "sign of peace". The Minister of Religious Affairs in Myanmar has promised to support the spread of the 969 movement. Wirathu's speeches attract thousands of people. His sermons are recorded on CDs and DVDs and sold in large numbers across the country. Many restaurants and shops also play them on loudspeakers. "The 969 Movement also spreads through Facebook and Youtube" (Routray, 2014). Ashin Wirathu is blamed for the recent violence against Muslims. His movement has been involved in harming the Rohingya Muslims. Wirathu thinks that the Rohingya population is growing quickly and that,

in the future, Muslims might become the majority in Myanmar, replacing the local Buddhists. “The cover story of the 20 June 2013 issue of Time Magazine called Wirathu “The Face of Buddhist Terror”.

Causes behind the Oppression against Rohingyas

Mental Constraints,

The mental constraints of Myanmar leaders are hard to crack quickly. People from Chittagong had massive economic influence in Burma at one time during the British colonialism. From history we have been informed that when the British conquered Arakan in the 18th century, there were very little people in the region, while the fertile Kaladan and Lemro River Valleys have a wide area for high yield agricultural land (Defence, 2014). Then, British strategy was to facilitate the migration of Bengali people from neighboring areas to the fertile valleys of Arakan as farmers. The British East India Company expanded the government of Bengal to Arakan, as the two countries had no overseas borders and no emigration limits.

Great majority of them first came as migrant farm workers and came back home after the harvest. The explanation for this was that the Bengalis were acceptable to the Indian colonial government while making the indigenous Arakanese too stubborn to rise twice in 1830 to the revolt (Hossain M. S., *Communal Conflict in Burma (1930-1940): Origins and Corollaries*, 2019). The influx of labor from Chittagong gave a significant boost to economic growth in Arakan, and the opening of routine commercial shipping in both Chittagong and Akyab was an economic achievement within a couple of decades. According to Myint Maung Tun “The Rohingya problem began with two operations conducted by Myanmar to address the increase of illegal immigrants: Naga Min (King Dragon) in 1978 and Pyi Thar Ya in 1991. In 1978, the Burma Socialist Program Party (BSPP) government under Ne Win carried out routine immigrant

checks in Rakhine state, particularly at the Bangladesh border where most illegal Bengalis live. These Bengalis speak almost the same Chittagonian dialect as the Chittagonians with slight variations in their accent, which is locally known as “Chatgaiya” and is a corrupt form of Bengali” (Tun, 2020)

During British rule, ethnic Bengali Indians played a big role in Burma’s government and economy. They worked as soldiers, civil servants, traders, and moneylenders. In simple terms, they were the main economic power in Burma at that time. For example, A.K. Khan became wealthy from business in Myanmar, and many of his children were born in Rangoon. The economic influence of Bengalis in Burma was significant.

However, the Theravada Buddhists in Burma did not accept this situation (Hossain M. S., *Bangladesh-Myanmar Relations; 1972-2010*, 2014). At that time, the Burmese people did not have the strength to fight against the British, but they disliked both the British and the Bengali Indians (Hossain M. S., *British Colonial Rule in Burma: An Analysis of Burmese Reaction*, 2021). As a result, anti-Indian riots started in 1930. Later, during the Japanese occupation of Burma, many Indians left the country. In 1962, the Burmese government forced many Indians to leave, reducing their role in Burma’s economy and society.

“Moreover, in Burma, the most popular hate-speech terms used against Rohingya, ‘kalar’ and ‘Bengali,’ both have roots in the colonial period of British rule from 1824 to 1948. Moreover, intellect persons of Myanmar believe that factors like this example generated anti-Indian sentiment and strengthened Burmese nationalism among Theravada Buddhists” (Kiersons, 2013). In 1930, a conflict over jobs at the Yangon port led to anti-Indian riots. Burmese workers blamed Indian workers for taking their jobs. As a result, violence broke out. During the riot, at least 200 Indian workers were killed and thrown into the river, while around 2,000 others were injured (Hossain

M. S., *Communal Conflict in Burma (1930-1940): Origins and Corollaries*, 2019). The British authorities used force against armed rioters who refused to surrender their weapons. The violence quickly spread across Burma, targeting Indians and Muslims.

In 1938, another riot took place due to growing anti-British and nationalist feelings. This time, around 204 Muslims were killed, more than 1,000 were injured, and 113 mosques were damaged. "The reason of oppression to the Rohingya is from the conflict between two different religions from the British period, which can be seen to function as a root of later conflicts" (Yegar, 1972) (Hossain M. S., *Communal Conflict in Burma (1930-1940): Origins and Corollaries*, 2019).

According to the International Crisis Group "The reason behind the Rohingya crisis is hatred toward the Rohingya Muslims aroused by the divide-and-conquer strategy during the British colonial period, which is also deeply related to the fact that Tatmadaw has been persecuting the Rohingya Muslims. During the period from 1988 to 1996, the Tatmadaw grew from 186,000 to 370,000 soldiers. About 14% of country's Gross Domestic Product (GDP) is spent on the military" (Group, 2016).

Citizenship Crisis

Myanmar began creating the legislation following the World War II. An eight year old individual born in Myanmar was eligible for full citizenship (1982 Myanmar Citizenship Law). According to this word, Muslims from Rohingya became permanent residents as they were born in Rakhine; hence registered as Myanmar citizens. They were eligible to vote and they were given the National Registration Certificates (NRCs). As Burmese citizens, they worked like other citizen in the administration and ministry of Government. The Union Citizenship Act also retained these services in 1948. In 1949, the Burmese citizen elections officer of Buthidaung, found that Muslims were not in fact eligible for

the certificate of nationality, because they were not really Burmese citizens. A reportable proposal was performed in the 1950s by the Burmese higher court (Rahman, 2021).

Premier U Nu said in 1954 that Rohingya is the ancestral race of Burma and has equal rights of nationality, such as Kashin, Kayah, Mon, Rakhine and Shan. Soon the language of Rohingya was introduced in radio broadcasting alongside various ethnic languages of Burma. A census in 1961 reported that Maunagdaw Muslims, Buthidaung and Ratheedaung were known in the Mayu regions as "Rohongya." Under the U Nu administration, a unique administrative zone for Rohingya was formed in Burma. But in 1962 the region was reversed by the General Ne Win. They deliberately and progressively abused their rights. There were two main acts that were constitutionalized to deny Rohingya's rights. The first in 1974 that was the "Emergency Immigration Act" and the second in 1982 the "Burmese Citizenship Law"

National Registration Certificate

In 1974, a 'National Registration Certificate' (NRCs) system based on ethnicity was initiated. Rohingyas are forced to eliminate from Myanmar's ethnic groups according to this system. The 1974 Emergency Immigration Act discriminates against Rohingyas by entitling them only to international identification cards; many colleges and organizations have refused to accept these NRCs, leaving the Rohingyas out of schooling and work opportunities. Citizenship was restricted in the 1974 Constitution to those whose parents were both citizens of Burma. There were quite a few Rohingyas who were qualifying for NRCs. The controversial 1982 Citizenship Law that established three types of citizenship forever deprived Rohingya the right to citizenship because all three groups were exempt from it. The absence of validity disqualified the NRC by cancelling them because of the absence of evidence of the history of their families and because they do not even speak Myanmar

national languages. There has been a form of white card given, but it cannot be confirmed as legal Burmese citizens. Those cards were eventually all discarded. They missed financial resources, jobs and even possession of land. The Rohingyas lost their right to vote in 2015 and were stateless.

Militancy

The fourth reason is fear, which comes from two main ideas: Some Rohingya groups, like the Arakan Rohingya National Organization (ARNO) and the Rohingya Solidarity Organization (RSO), were linked to members of Al-Qaeda and the Taliban (SELTH, 2004). Buddhists believed that the Muslim population was growing very fast. Because of these reasons, Buddhist monks became worried. They feared that Muslims might become the majority and take over their society.

“This fourth reason is the antagonism that the military junta manipulated as a political instrument to retain their regime by diverting the public attention from discontent with autocratic policies to the Rohingya issue, particularly during the military regime” (Yunus, 1994). On May 28, 2012, a 27-year-old Buddhist woman named Thida Htwe was reportedly raped and killed by three Muslim men in Ramri Township, located in southern Arakan State (Ismail, 2012). This incident led to new violence in the area. In response, around 100 Rohingya were killed, including 10 Muslim pilgrims traveling on a bus in Toungop. Additionally, 120,000 people were forced to leave their homes (Economist, 2012). On October 9, 2016, around 400 Rohingya militants attacked three Border Guard Police (BGP) posts in Maungdaw and Rathedaung. They were armed with knives and slingshots. During the attack, they killed nine police officers and took 62 firearms and 10,000 rounds of ammunition. Between October 10 and 12, they also killed four Myanmar soldiers (Group, 2016). “In the respond to the attacks, on 10 October 2016, the GoM blocked all humanitarian aid to

the Rohingya” (Solomon, 2016). On November 12, a lieutenant colonel was killed, and several others were injured by 60 armed Rohingya militants. After this attack, security forces destroyed 1,500 Rohingya homes, and helicopters shot randomly into Rohingya villages. More than 100 Rohingya people died, and over 90,000 fled Myanmar (Group, 2016).

The present Rohingyah exodus started after attacking at 30 defense encampments along the territory with Bangladesh on 25 August 2017 and were brutally killed a dozen of Burmese policemen and at least one Tatmadaw soldier by the Arakan Rohingya Salvation Army (ARSA). In reaction, the first time that Myanmar used such a statement for an insurgent group that ARSA was publicly announced a terrorist association.

Geo-political Issues

The Rohingya crisis includes critical persecution of the Rohingya Muslim minority in Myanmar. Regional politics, particularly from China and India, have an effect on this example. Myanmar is close to China and has a lot of energy. It helps China receive oil and gas without using sea traits such as Malacca Strait, controlled by the US Navy. Using Myanmar saves money and time by cutting a distance of about 3000 kilometers and reducing travel time by six days (Topcu, 2020). Myanmar also has its own oil and gas, so China not only has to trust the Middle East. China is already using Myanmar pipelines to get gas and oil. It also supports China's belt and road plan to improve trade routes. Moreover, in international gatherings, China assists Myanmar. In order to demonstrate its dominance in Southeast Asia, it defends Myanmar against complaints of violations of human rights. China handles Rohingya refugees at its border by limiting their movement and strengthening security, with a focus on national stability.

Map-1,

Source: <https://www.chinacenter.net/2020/china-currents/19-3/a-relationship-on-a-pipeline-china-and-myanmar/>

On the other hand, The Rohingya crisis, particularly along its northeastern border, has raised concerns in India about instability. Tensions with local businesses may increase as a result of refugees. India has provided some humanitarian resources to Rohingya refugees. Nonetheless, it has stringent immigration laws and focuses on border security. India attempts to maintain strong ties with Bangladesh and Myanmar while striking a balance. It considers humanitarian needs while simultaneously defending Myanmar's authority. China's pastimes are linked to the Rohingya crisis.

Religion

In Buddhist-majority Myanmar, particularly in Rakhine State, the Rohingya are primarily Muslims. Despite having lived in Myanmar for many generations, they have historically been viewed as outsiders by many. Due in part to religious othering, the state and a large number of citizens portray the Rohingya as illegal "Bengali" immigrants. Over the past few decades, Myanmar has seen a rise in militant Buddhist nationalism. Anti-Muslim sentiment has been stoked by certain monks and political organizations that have incited fear that Islam poses a threat to Buddhism. Ma Ba Tha, an officially defunct

organization that continues to have informal influence, has been accused of inciting hatred against Muslims, including the Rohingya.

The 1982 Citizenship Law excluded

the Rohingya from the list of recognized ethnic groups, denying them citizenship. Their Muslim identity contributed to the rationale for exclusion, differentiating them from other ethnic minorities in Myanmar. Religious Justification for Violence While the violence has ethnic and political dimensions; religion has been used to justify actions both by mobs and by some state actors. Mass killings, arson, and rape during the 2017 crackdown were often accompanied by rhetoric demonizing Muslims. But religion alone doesn't explain it ethnicity, colonial history, nationalism, geopolitics, and resource competition also play crucial roles.

Cultural identity

To justify crackdowns and denial of citizenship, Myanmar's military and political elites have portrayed the Rohingya's cultural and religious practices as at odds with "national identity." Cultural Markers as Dehumanizing Tools: Different clothing, language, and religious practices have been used to "other" the Rohingya and to advance the notion that they do not belong in Myanmar. In conclusion, the crisis is not a result of Rohingya culture. Rather, it is the focus of ultranationalist rhetoric and discrimination spearheaded by the state. Ethnic cleansing, statelessness, and systematic violence have all been justified by manipulating their cultural identity (Chickera, 2021). The identity of the Rohingya people is multi-layered. There are 135 ethnic groups that reside in Myanmar and the Rohingya are one of them. Furthermore, the Rohingya people have a distinct language. The identifying language of the Rohingya people is a dialect of Bengali known as Chittagonian and which is not spoken in the rest of Myanmar. Some records from 1799 and 1815 indicate that the Rohingya or Rooinga, which is also an Arakanese word, were the original inhabitants of what we currently call Rakhine State (Buchanan, 2003). Some academics suggest that this language is an Indo-Aryan language. On the contrary, the Rohingya claim that they have origins in Rakhine and not illegal migrant or Bengali and they are

preferring to all themselves Rakhine Muslims (Laider, 2013). A number of Burmese people argue, without bases, that the Bangladeshi and Pakistani cultures have heavily influenced Rohingya culture and food. Unfortunately most of the buddhist population refer to the Rohingya using the slang term kalar. This adds to the very complex identity issue.

Lack of Education among Rohingya

Before the military takeover in 1962, Rohingya Muslims were on par with their Buddhist counterparts in terms of education. However, due to on-going poverty, severe discrimination, and relentless persecution, the number of Rohingya students has significantly dropped. Gaining admission to colleges and universities for higher education has become a real challenge for the Rohingya community. They face strict limitations when it comes to pursuing professional courses, largely due to citizenship issues. While there are several voluntary religious schools that provide education to a portion of Rohingya students, these institutions struggle to modernize their teaching methods due to various restrictions, lack of funding, and inadequate facilities. As a result, they often fail to produce skilled students or capable workers for society. Many Rohingyas living in exile find it difficult to provide education for their children.

Lack of Political Participation among Rohingya

Before 1962, the Rohingya community was recognized as an indigenous ethnic group in Burma, with representatives in the Burmese parliament and some even holding ministerial and high government positions. However, after the military seized power, they were systematically stripped of their political rights. The controversial citizenship law enacted in 1982 declared them non-nationals or foreign residents. Ironically, despite this declaration, the military could not prevent the Rohingyas from participating in the multi-party elections of 1990, although the results were never acknowledged by the military junta.

Today, the Rohingyas live in dire conditions, facing an uncertain future, and are treated as if they are a people destined for extermination.

Conclusion

The Rohingya crisis is one of the longest, complex and multidimensional humanitarian calamities of today's world. Due to long centuries of historical migration, cultural diffusion and political change, the Rohingya have undergone an identity, a cultural identity that they have determined on their own, throughout the Arakanese region. Our study shows that, contrary to popular belief, the Rohingyas are not recent migrants, but descendants of Arab traders, Persian missionaries, Mughal soldiers and Bengali settlers who have been with us since more than a millennium. Relatively few successive governments of Myanmar, particularly after independence, have abandoned them, particularly through institutionalized discrimination, climaxed in the 1982 Citizenship Law, which effectively made the Rohingya stateless.

It is attested through qualitative methods and through use of primary and secondary sources that the crisis here not only presents itself as a modern political phenomenon but also represents the result of decades of structural violence and socio-political exclusion underpinned by colonial legacies, nationalist ideologies and geopolitical interests. Also, the narratives from the ground, the narratives from refugees, local communities and officials, contribute to the understanding of the crisis.

Furthermore, the findings affirm that the Rohingya crisis is not only a national problem for Myanmar but, more generally, a serious security and humanitarian challenge for Bangladesh and for the wider South and Southeast Asian region, with effects such as strain on local infrastructure, the spread of transnational crime, and rising instability at the frontiers.

We think a sustainable response should have firstly a historical and ethnic legitimacy foundation, and Myanmar should adopt, or at the very least modify, exclusionary legislation (particularly the 1982 Citizenship Act), and recognize the Rohingya as legitimate citizens with respect for all civil, political and cultural rights. At the same time, the regional and international actors should build on their diplomatic and humanitarian capacities and

intensify pressure mechanisms for accountability and reform. This study fills a significant research vacuum by providing a historical-rooted, empirically-based and security-oriented analysis of the Rohingya crisis whose aim is both to be used not only in academic discourse but also in practical policy efforts to resolve one of the most urgent refugee crises of our day.

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